

The diseased plants were stunted; leaves were ragged and smaller than normal ones; and flag leaves were deformed. Severely infected plants did not produce healthy grains and had

incomplete panicle emergence. Yield losses ranged from 80 to 100%. Dr. E. A. Heinrichs of IRRI identified the disease in the field as caused by ragged stunt virus.

Ragged stunt incidence was further noted in 17 cultures grown in the field at that time. The percentage of ragged stunt-infected hills is presented in the table. □

Varietal resistance to neck blast in rice

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Blast *Pyricularia oryzae* is one of the most damaging rice diseases in the hills of Uttar Pradesh, India. During kharif 1977, two coordinated Uniform Variety Trials of

rice were conducted at the Rice Research Station, Majhera, Nainital district. Severe neck blast incidence was scored on a scale of 1 to 9. Only 5 entries were resistant (see table). China 988 and China 1039, which have high cold tolerance, were highly susceptible to neck blast. The observations point out a major weakness in the composition of the hill trials. The entries should be thoroughly screened against diseases before promotion to advanced yield

trials. This is particularly necessary in the Uttar Pradesh hills, where all representative races of the pathogen have been reported. □

Reaction of varieties to neck blast in the field. Uttar Pradesh, India.

Reaction ^a	Entries (no.)	Designation
Resistant	5	K17-9-1-1, K30-82-B-1, K35-67-2-1-3-1, K42-115-1-2-1-2, R × T 42.
Moderately resistant	5	K21-9-10-1, K26-2-36, K28-1, K42-86-B-2-1, KH6159.
Susceptible to highly susceptible	23	K17-BK-1-3-1, K18-6-B-2-1-2, K28-KH74, K28-48-B-2, K31-163-3, K39-96-3-1-1-1-2, K41-146-1, K41-105-2, K42-15-1-1-3-3, K46-15-13-2-24-1-1, K46-15-B-2-1, K84, K102-51-10, K102-42-2-1, K143-17-3, K178, K229-59, KR17254, KH7164, China972, China 988, China 1039, IR579-ES-29.

^aScore of 1-3 = resistant, 5 = moderately resistant, 7-9 = susceptible to highly susceptible.

Field reaction of upland rainfed paddy varieties to various diseases in Karnataka, India

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The reactions of a few selected varieties to natural infection by various diseases were tested at selected locations during kharif 1977. The table shows the variability of the varieties' reactions to different diseases at different locations, under irrigated and rainfed conditions. □

Reactions of upland paddy varieties to various diseases in Karnataka, India.

Designation	Origin	Reaction to diseases ^a at									
		Mandya		Hebbal			Ponnampet				
		LB	NB	LB	NB	BB	BLS	LB	NB	Rhy	Hel
M161	Sel. from Mugad (local)	-	S	-	-	M	-	-	-	M	M
M249	-do-	L	S	M	S	S	M	M	S	M	M
M141	-do-	-	-	M	-	S	M	M	-	-	M
M81	-do-	L	S	-	S	M	L	M	S	-	M
HY258-1	280-51-36/M141	-	M	L	S	M	-	S	S	M	M
HY449-17	M141/Y-4	-	S	L	S	S	L	S	-	-	M
HY26-10	M141/Y-4	L	M	-	S	M	M	S	-	-	M
HY256	A200/475-36	L	M	L	S	S	L	S	S	M	-
HY249-13-1	280-51-36/M-141	L	M	-	S	M	L	S	S	-	M
Waner 1	Sel. from Waner	-	M	M	S	M	M	M	S	S	S
K44-1	Sel. from Kagasal	-	L	-	M	M	L	S	S	-	-
D6-2-2	Sel. from Dodigya	L	-	-	-	S	L	M	M	M	M
Y4	Sel. from Yelikerisal	-	-	-	-	M	M	S	M	-	M
A200	Sel. from Antarsal	M	-	-	-	M	M	S	M	-	-
A67	-do-	-	-	-	-	M	M	M	M	-	M
A90	-do-	L	M	-	S	M	L	M	M	-	S

^aLB = leaf blast, NB = neck blast, BB = bacterial blight, BLS = bacterial leaf streak, Rhy = Rhynchosporium, Hel = Helminthosporium, L = low disease rating, M = medium disease rating, S = severe disease rating.